

Improved filtering H_∞ finite frequency of Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy systems

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ABSTRACT

The work treats the filter H_∞ finite frequency (FF) in Takagi-Sugeno (T-S) two-dimensional (2-D) systems described by Fornasini-Marchesini local state-space (FM LSS) models. The goal of this work is to find an FF H_∞ T-S fuzzy filter model design in such a way that the error system is stable and has a reduced FF H_∞ performance over FF areas with noise is established as a prerequisite. Via the use of the generalized Kalman Yakubovich Popov (gKYP) lemma, Lyapunov functions approach, Finsler's lemma, and parameterize slack matrices, new design conditions guaranteeing the FF H_∞ T-S fuzzy filter method of FM LSS models are developed by solving linear matrix inequalities (LMIs). At last, the simulation results are provided to show the effectiveness and the validity of the proposed FF T-S fuzzy of FM LSS models strategy by a practical application has been made.

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NOMENCLATURE

- " T " : Matrix transposition
- " $*$ " : Matrix symmetry
- $M > 0$: matrix M is positive
- $\text{sym}(M)$: $M + M^T$
- $\text{diag}\{..\}$: Block diagonal matrix

1. INTRODUCTION

During the latter decennary, various searchers studied two-dimensional (2-D) systems inclusive discrete and continuous adjustments have a lot of practices in engineering as though process control, digital filter, and image processing [1]-[4]. Many important results based on LMI approach have already been reported. Among these results, such as [5]-[16]. The main existing sources on filtering problems and disturbances are based on the whole full frequency (EF) area, which will give several types of filtering design [15], [16]. However, most practical industrial applications work in a FF domain. So far, a few applications have been made [17]-[24]. Thus, for this we will present new approaches to solve these problems. The primary goal of our work is to define a fuzzy filter of discrete Fornasini-Marchesini models over FF ranges such a way that the error model is stable and have a reduced H_∞ FF index of a noise is established as a prerequisite. We have also presented an example of simulation in order to exemplify the efficiency of the suggested method.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

2.1. System formulation

Envisage the nonlinear FMLSS presented by:

Rule 1: if $\zeta_1(s)$ is $\tilde{M}_1^l$, ... and $\zeta_\theta(s)$ is $\tilde{M}_\theta^l$, then,

$$\begin{aligned} x_{n+1,k+1} &= A_{1l}x_{n,k+1} + A_{2l}x_{n+1,k} + B_{1l}u_{n,k+1} + B_{2l}u_{n+1,k} \\ y_{n,k} &= C_l x_{n,k} + D_l u_{n,k} \\ z_{n,k} &= E_l x_{n,k} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $(\tilde{M}_1^l, \dots, \tilde{M}_\zeta^l)$ are fuzzy sets; $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is state vector; $y \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ is measured output; $z \in \mathbb{R}^z$ is a signal to estimated; $u \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is supposed to appertain to a renowned rectangular domain Ω , where is the recognized noise signal and located in the following sets of frequencies:

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega &\triangleq \{(\mu_1, \mu_2) \in \mathbb{R} | \mu_1^a \leq \mu_1 \leq \mu_1^b; \mu_2^a \leq \mu_2 \leq \mu_2^b; \\ &\mu_1^a, \mu_2^a, \mu_1^b, \mu_2^b \in [-\pi, \pi]\} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where $\mu_1^a, \mu_1^b, \mu_2^a$ and μ_2^b are known scalars. We describe the nonlinear system (1) employ singleton fuzzifier, center-average and inference product by the following relation:

$$\begin{aligned} x_{n+1,k+1} &= A_1(q)x_{n,k+1} + A_2(q)x_{n+1,k} + B_1(q)u_{n,k+1} + B_2(q)u_{n+1,k} \\ y_{n,k} &= C(q)x_{n,k} + D(q)u_{n,k} \\ z_{n,k} &= E(q)x_{n,k} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_1(q) & B_1(q) \\ A_2(q) & B_2(q) \\ C(q) & D(q) \\ E(q) & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{l=1}^r q_l(\zeta(s)) \begin{bmatrix} A_{1l} & B_{1l} \\ A_{2l} & B_{2l} \\ C_l & D_l \\ E_l & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

In this work, a fuzzy filter is designed ie being as:

Rule 1: if $\zeta_1(s)$ is $\tilde{M}_1^l$, ... and $\zeta_\theta(k)$ is $\tilde{M}_\theta^l$, then,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{x}_{n+1,k+1} &= \hat{A}_{1l}\hat{x}_{i,k+1} + \hat{A}_{2l}\hat{x}_{i+1,k} + \hat{B}_{1l}y_{n,k} + \hat{B}_{2l}y_{n,k} \\ \hat{z}_{n,k} &= \hat{C}_l\hat{x}_{n,k} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{x}_{n,k}$ is state filter vector; $\hat{z}_{n,k}$ estimation of $z_{n,k}$; $\hat{A}_{1l}, \hat{A}_{2l}, \hat{B}_{1l}, \hat{B}_{2l}, \hat{C}_l$ are parameters should be defined. We get defuzzified for system (5) is being as:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{x}_{n+1,k+1} &= \hat{A}_1(q)\hat{x}_{n,k+1} + \hat{A}_2(q)x_{n+1,k} + \hat{B}_1(q)y_{n,k} + \hat{B}_2(q)y_{n,k} \\ \hat{z}_{n,k} &= \hat{C}(q)\hat{x}_{n,k} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

with

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{A}_1(q) & \hat{B}_1(q) \\ \hat{A}_2(q) & \hat{B}_2(q) \\ \hat{C}(q) & \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{l=1}^r h_l(\theta(k)) \begin{bmatrix} \hat{A}_{1l} & \hat{B}_{1l} \\ \hat{A}_{2l} & \hat{B}_{2l} \\ \hat{C}_l & \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Let $\xi_{n,k} := [x_{n,q}^T \ \check{x}_{n,q}^T]^T$, $\mathbf{e}_{n,k} = \mathbf{y}_{n,k} - \check{y}_{n,k}$, Then, the error model as shown in:

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_{n+1,k+1} &= \bar{A}_1(q)\xi_{n,k+1} + \bar{B}_1(q)u_{n,k+1} + \bar{A}_2(q)\xi_{n+1,k} + \bar{B}_2(q)u_{n+1,k} \\ \mathbf{e}_{n,k} &= \bar{C}(q)\xi_{n,k} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{A}_1(q) &= \begin{pmatrix} A_1(q) & 0\hat{B}_1(q)C(q) \\ \hat{A}_1(q) & \end{pmatrix}; \bar{B}_1(q) = \begin{pmatrix} B_1(q) \\ \hat{B}_1(q)D(q) \end{pmatrix}; \bar{B}_2(q) = \begin{pmatrix} B_2(q) \\ \hat{B}_2(q)D(q) \end{pmatrix}; \\ \bar{A}_2(q) &= \begin{pmatrix} A_2(q) & 0 \\ \hat{B}_2(q)C(q) & \hat{A}_2(q) \end{pmatrix}; \bar{C}(q) = (E(q) \quad -\hat{C}(q)) \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

We express the question of this work by: we design an appropriate fuzzy filter (6) such that a error model is well-posed, stable satisfies the FF index:

$$\sup_{0 \neq u_{n,k} \in l_2\{[0,\infty), [0,\infty)\}} \|e_{n,k}\|_2 \leq \gamma^2 \|u_{n,k}\|_2 \tag{10}$$

A equation is applicable of (8) knowing the following hold:

$$\begin{aligned} e^{j\mu_3^b} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} [(e^{j\mu_3^b} \xi_{n,k+1} - \xi_{n+1,k+1})^T (\xi_{n+1,k+1} - e^{j\mu_1^a} \xi_{n,k+1})] &\geq 0 \\ e^{j\mu_4^b} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} [(\xi_{n+1,k+1} - e^{j\mu_2^b} \xi_{n+1,k})^T (e^{j\mu_2^a} \xi_{n+1,k} - \xi_{n+1,k+1})] &\geq 0 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

2.2. Preliminaries

Lemma 2..1 in [25] from (12), we could get (13).

$$\begin{bmatrix} T + MU + U^T M^T & * \\ -M^T + GU & V - G - G^T \end{bmatrix} < 0 \tag{12}$$

$$T + U^T V U < 0 \tag{13}$$

Lemma 2..2 in [19] error system (8) is stable and FF in (10) is fulfilled, on condition that there are $P_1, P_2, 0 < Q_1, 0 < Q_2$, satisfying.

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{C}(q)^T \mathcal{C}(q) & \mathcal{C}(q)^T \mathcal{D}(q) \\ \mathcal{D}(q)^T \mathcal{C}(q) & -\gamma^2 I + \mathcal{D}(q)^T \mathcal{D}(q) \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{A}(q) & \mathcal{B}(q) \\ I & 0 \end{pmatrix}^T \begin{pmatrix} P & \Lambda^* Q \\ Q \Lambda & -\mathcal{R} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{A}(q) & \mathcal{B}(q) \\ I & 0 \end{pmatrix} < 0 \tag{14}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R} &= \begin{pmatrix} P_1 + 2\cos(\mu_3^b)Q_1 & 0 \\ 0 & P_2 + 2\cos(\mu_4^b)Q_2 \end{pmatrix}; \mathcal{D}(q) = \begin{pmatrix} \bar{D}(q) & 0 \\ 0 & \bar{D}(q) \end{pmatrix}; \mathcal{A}(q) = (\bar{A}_1(q) \quad \bar{A}_2(q)); \\ Q &= (Q_1 \quad Q_2); P = P_1 + P_2; \Lambda = \begin{pmatrix} e^{-j\mu_3^a} I_{2\bar{n}} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-j\mu_4^a} I_{2\bar{n}} \end{pmatrix}; \mathcal{B}(q) = (\bar{B}_1(q) \quad \bar{B}_2(q)); \\ \mathcal{C}(q) &= \begin{pmatrix} \bar{C}(q) & 0 \\ 0 & \bar{C}(q) \end{pmatrix}; \mu_4^a = \frac{\mu_2^a + \mu_2^b}{2}; \mu_3^b = \frac{\mu_1^b - \mu_1^a}{2}; \mu_4^b = \frac{\mu_2^b - \mu_2^a}{2}; \mu_3^a = \frac{\mu_1^a + \mu_1^b}{2}; \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

3. FF PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

3.1. Theorem 3..1

Error model (8) is stable, FF index (10) is fulfilled, on condition that there are $P, Q, W_1, W_2, M_1, M_2, G_1, G_2, F_1, H$ satisfying $Q_1 > 0, Q_2 > 0, W_1 > 0, W_2 > 0$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi &= \begin{bmatrix} \Phi_{11} & \Phi_{12} & \mathcal{A}^T(q)G_1^T - M_1 & \mathcal{A}^T(q)G_2^T & \mathcal{C}^T \\ * & \Phi_{22} & \mathcal{B}^T(q)G_1^T - M_2 & \mathcal{B}^T(q)G_2^T & \mathcal{D}^T \\ * & * & P - G_1 - G_1^T & \Lambda^* Q - G_2^T & 0 \\ * & * & * & -\mathcal{R} & 0 \\ * & * & * & * & -I \end{bmatrix} < 0 \\ \Upsilon &= \begin{bmatrix} -W_1 + sym(F_1 \bar{A}_1(q)) & F_1 \bar{A}_2(q) & -F_1 + \bar{A}_1^T(q)^T H^T \\ * & -W_2 & \bar{A}_2^T(q)^T H^T \\ * & * & W_1 + W_2 - sym(q) \end{bmatrix} < 0 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

$$\Phi_{11} = M_1\mathcal{A}(q) + \mathcal{A}^T(q)M_1^T; \Phi_{12} = M_1\mathcal{B}(q) + \mathcal{A}^T(q)M_2^T; \Phi_{22} = -\gamma^2 I + M_2\mathcal{B}(q) + \mathcal{B}^T(q)M_2^T;$$

3.2. Proof 3.2

First, condition (14) maybe written as

$$T + N^T V N < 0 \tag{17}$$

Where

$$N = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{A}(q) & \mathcal{B}(q) \\ I & 0 \end{bmatrix}; V = \begin{bmatrix} P & \Lambda^* Q \\ Q\Lambda & -\mathcal{R} \end{bmatrix}; T = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{C}(q)^T \mathcal{C}(q) & \mathcal{C}(q)^T \mathcal{D}(q) \\ \mathcal{D}(q)^T \mathcal{C}(q) & -\gamma^2 I + \mathcal{D}(q)^T \mathcal{D}(q) \end{bmatrix} \tag{18}$$

By using Lemma 2, (17) is equivalent to

$$\begin{bmatrix} T + MU + U^T M^T & U^T G^T - M \\ -M^T + GU & V - G - G^T \end{bmatrix} < 0 \tag{19}$$

with

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} M_1 & 0 \\ M_2 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; G = \begin{bmatrix} G_1 & 0 \\ G_2 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \tag{20}$$

which, using Schur complement, leads to given (16). Consider the Lyapunov equation, such that

$$\begin{pmatrix} W_1 & 0 \\ 0 & W_2 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \bar{A}_1(q) & \bar{A}_2(q) \end{pmatrix}^T (W_1 + W_2) \begin{pmatrix} \bar{A}_1(q) & \bar{A}_2(q) \end{pmatrix} > 0 \tag{21}$$

Where

$$\hat{U} = \begin{pmatrix} \bar{A}_1(q) & \bar{A}_2(q) \end{pmatrix}; \hat{T} = \begin{pmatrix} -W_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -W_2 \end{pmatrix}; \hat{V} = W_1 + W_2 \tag{22}$$

We chose F is being as:

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} F_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}^T \tag{23}$$

4. FF PERFORMANCE DESIGN

4.1. Theorem 4.1

Error model (8) is stable, FF index (10) is fulfilled, on condition that there are $\hat{A}_{1i}, \hat{B}_{1i}, \hat{A}_{2i}, \hat{B}_{2i}, \hat{C}_{1i}, \hat{D}_{1i}, M_{1u}, G_{2u}, M_{2t}, G_{1t}, H_{1t}, F_{1t}, V, u = 1, 2, 3, 4, t = 1, 2, P_{1s}, Q_{1s} > 0, W_{1s} > 0, P_{2s}, Q_{2s} > 0, W_{2s} > 0, s = 1, 2, 3$, satisfying.

$$\tilde{\Delta} = \left[\begin{array}{c|c} \tilde{\Delta}_1 & \tilde{\Delta}_2 \\ * & \tilde{\Delta}_3 \end{array} \right] < 0; \tag{24}$$

$$\tilde{\Omega} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\Omega}_{11} & \tilde{\Omega}_{12} & \tilde{\Omega}_{13} & E\hat{A}_{2i} & \tilde{\Omega}_{15} & \tilde{\Omega}_{16} \\ * & \tilde{\Omega}_{22} & \tilde{\Omega}_{23} & \hat{A}_{2i}^T & \tilde{\Omega}_{25} & \tilde{\Omega}_{26} \\ * & * & -W_{21} & -W_{22} & \tilde{\Omega}_{35} & A_{2j}^T H_{12}^T \\ * & * & * & -W_{23} & \tilde{\Omega}_{45} & \hat{A}_{2i}^T \\ * & * & * & * & \tilde{\Omega}_{55} & \tilde{\Omega}_{56} \\ * & * & * & * & * & \tilde{\Omega}_{66} \end{bmatrix} < 0 \tag{25}$$

with

$$\tilde{\Delta}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\Delta}_{111} & \tilde{\Delta}_{112} & \tilde{\Delta}_{113} & \tilde{\Delta}_{114} & \tilde{\Delta}_{115} & \tilde{\Delta}_{116} \\ * & \tilde{\Delta}_{122} & M_{12}A_{2j} & sym[\hat{A}_{2i}] & \tilde{\Delta}_{125} & \tilde{\Delta}_{126} \\ * & * & \tilde{\Delta}_{133} & A_{2j}^T M_{14}^T & \tilde{\Delta}_{135} & \tilde{\Delta}_{136} \\ * & * & * & \tilde{\Delta}_{144} & \tilde{\Delta}_{145} & \tilde{\Delta}_{146} \\ * & * & * & * & \tilde{\Delta}_{155} & \tilde{\Delta}_{156} \\ * & * & * & * & * & \tilde{\Delta}_{166} \end{bmatrix};$$

$$\tilde{\Delta}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\Delta}_{11} & \tilde{\Delta}_{12} & \tilde{\Delta}_{13} & \tilde{\Delta}_{14} & \tilde{\Delta}_{15} & \tilde{\Delta}_{16} & \tilde{\Delta}_{17} & 0 \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{21} & \tilde{\Delta}_{22} & \tilde{\Delta}_{23} & \tilde{\Delta}_{24} & 0 & \tilde{\Delta}_{26} & 0 & \tilde{\Delta}_{88} \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{31} & \tilde{\Delta}_{32} & \tilde{\Delta}_{33} & \tilde{\Delta}_{34} & \tilde{\Delta}_{35} & \tilde{\Delta}_{36} & \tilde{\Delta}_{37} & 0 \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{41} & \tilde{\Delta}_{42} & \tilde{\Delta}_{43} & \tilde{\Delta}_{44} & 0 & \tilde{\Delta}_{46} & 0 & -\hat{C}_i^T \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{51} & \tilde{\Delta}_{52} & \tilde{\Delta}_{53} & \tilde{\Delta}_{54} & \tilde{\Delta}_{55} & \tilde{\Delta}_{56} & \tilde{\Delta}_{57} & 0 \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{61} & \tilde{\Delta}_{62} & \tilde{\Delta}_{63} & \tilde{\Delta}_{64} & \tilde{\Delta}_{65} & \tilde{\Delta}_{66} & 0 & \tilde{\Delta}_{88} \end{bmatrix};$$

$$\tilde{\Delta}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\Delta}_{311} & \tilde{\Delta}_{312} & \tilde{\Delta}_{313} & \tilde{\Delta}_{314} & \tilde{\Delta}_{315} & \tilde{\Delta}_{316} & 0 & 0 \\ * & \tilde{\Delta}_{322} & \tilde{\Delta}_{323} & \tilde{\Delta}_{324} & \tilde{\Delta}_{325} & \tilde{\Delta}_{326} & 0 & 0 \\ * & * & \tilde{\Delta}_{333} & \tilde{\Delta}_{334} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ * & * & * & \tilde{\Delta}_{344} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ * & * & * & * & \tilde{\Delta}_{355} & \tilde{\Delta}_{356} & 0 & 0 \\ * & * & * & * & * & \tilde{\Delta}_{366} & 0 & 0 \\ * & * & * & * & * & * & -I & 0 \\ * & * & * & * & * & * & * & -I \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Omega}_{13} &= F_{11}A_{2j}; \bar{\Omega}_{23} = F_{12}A_{2j}; \bar{\Omega}_{35} = A_{2j}^T H_{11}^T; \bar{\Omega}_{45} = \hat{A}_{2i}^T E^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{122} = sym[\hat{A}_{1i}]; \tilde{\Delta}_{133} = sym[E\hat{A}_{2j}]; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{216} &= A_{1j}^T G_{24}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{288} = D_j^T - \hat{D}_i^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{217} = C_j^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{288} = -\hat{C}_i^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{133} = sym[M_{13}A_{2j}]; \tilde{\Delta}_{237} = C_j^T; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{111} &= sym[M_{11}A_{1j}]; \tilde{\Delta}_{112} = A_{1j}^T M_{12}^T + E\hat{A}_{1i}; \tilde{\Delta}_{113} = M_{11}A_{2j} + A_{1j}^T M_{13}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{114} = A_{2j}^T M_{14}^T + E\hat{A}_{2i}; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{115} &= M_{11}B_{1j} + A_{1j}^T M_{21}^T + E\hat{B}_{1i}; \tilde{\Delta}_{116} = M_{11}B_{2j} + A_{1j}^T M_{22}^T + E\hat{B}_{2i}; \tilde{\Delta}_{125} = M_{12}B_{1j} + \hat{B}_{1i}; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{126} &= M_{12}B_{2j} + \hat{B}_{2i}; \tilde{\Delta}_{135} = M_{13}B_{1j} + A_{2j}^T M_{21}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{156} = M_{21}B_{2j} + B_{1j}^T M_{22}^T; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{136} &= M_{13}B_{2j} + A_{2j}^T M_{22}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{145} = M_{14}B_{1j} + E\hat{B}_{1i}; \tilde{\Delta}_{146} = M_{14}B_{2j}; \tilde{\Delta}_{155} = -\gamma^2 I + sym[M_{21}B_{1j}]; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{166} &= -\gamma^2 I + sym[M_{22}B_{2j}]; \tilde{\Delta}_{11} = A_{1j}^T G_{11}^T - M_{11}; \tilde{\Delta}_{12} = A_{1j}^T G_{12}^T - EV; \tilde{\Delta}_{13} = A_{1j}^T G_{21}^T; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{14} &= A_{1j}^T G_{22}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{15} = A_{1j}^T G_{23}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{16} = A_{1j}^T G_{24}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{21} = \hat{A}_{1i}^T E^T - M_{12}; \tilde{\Delta}_{22} = \hat{A}_{1i}^T - V; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{23} &= \hat{A}_{1i}^T E^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{24} = \hat{A}_{1i}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{26} = \hat{A}_{1i}^T E^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{31} = A_{2j}^T G_{11}^T - M_{13}; \tilde{\Delta}_{32} = A_{2j}^T G_{12}^T; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{33} &= A_{2j}^T G_{21}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{34} = A_{2j}^T G_{22}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{35} = A_{2j}^T G_{23}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{36} = A_{2j}^T G_{24}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{41} = \hat{A}_{2i}^T E^T - M_{14}; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{22} &= \hat{A}_{2i}^T - V; \tilde{\Delta}_{23} = \hat{A}_{2i}^T E^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{24} = \hat{A}_{2i}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{26} = \hat{A}_{2i}^T E^T; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{51} &= B_{1j}^T G_{11}^T + \hat{B}_{1i}^T E^T - M_{21}; \tilde{\Delta}_{52} = B_{1j}^T G_{12}^T + \hat{B}_{1i}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{53} = B_{1j}^T G_{21}^T + \hat{B}_{1i}^T E^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{54} = B_{1j}^T G_{22}^T + \hat{B}_{1i}^T; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{55} &= B_{1j}^T G_{23}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{56} = B_{1j}^T G_{24}^T + \hat{B}_{1i}^T E^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{61} = B_{2j}^T G_{11}^T - M_{22}; \tilde{\Delta}_{62} = B_{2j}^T G_{12}^T + \hat{B}_{2i}^T; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{63} &= B_{2j}^T G_{21}^T + \hat{B}_{2i}^T E^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{64} = B_{2j}^T G_{22}^T + \hat{B}_{2i}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{65} = B_{2j}^T G_{23}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{66} = B_{2j}^T G_{24}^T + \hat{B}_{2i}^T E^T; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{311} &= P_{11} + P_{21} - G_{11} - G_{11}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{313} = e^{-j\mu_3^a} Q_{11} - G_{21}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{312} = P_{12} + P_{22} - EV - G_{21}^T; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{314} &= e^{-j\mu_3^a} Q_{12} - G_{22}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{315} = e^{-j\mu_3^a} Q_{21} - G_{23}^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{316} = e^{-j\mu_3^a} Q_{22} - G_{24}^T; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{322} &= P_{13} + P_{23} - V - V^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{323} = e^{-j\mu_4^a} Q_{21}^T - V^T E^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{324} = e^{-j\mu_4^a} Q_{13} - V^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{325} = e^{-j\mu_4^a} Q_{22}^T; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{326} &= e^{-j\mu_4^a} Q_{23} - V^T E^T; \tilde{\Delta}_{333} = -P_{11} - 2cos(\mu_3^b)Q_{11}; \tilde{\Delta}_{334} = -P_{12} - 2cos(\mu_3^b)Q_{12}; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{344} &= P_{13} - 2cos(\mu_3^b)Q_{13}; \tilde{\Delta}_{355} = -P_{21} - 2cos(\mu_3^b)Q_{21}; \tilde{\Delta}_{356} = -P_{22} - 2cos(\mu_3^b)Q_{22}; \\ \tilde{\Delta}_{366} &= -P_{23} - 2cos(\mu_3^b)Q_{23}; \bar{\Omega}_{12} = -W_{12} + A_{1j}^T F_{12}^T + E\hat{A}_{1i}; \bar{\Omega}_{11} = -W_{11} + sym(F_{11}A_{1j}); \\ \bar{\Omega}_{22} &= -W_{13} + sym(\hat{A}_{1i}); \bar{\Omega}_{15} = -F_{11} + A_{1j}^T H_{11}^T; \bar{\Omega}_{16} = -EV + A_{1j}^T H_{12}^T; \bar{\Omega}_{25} = -F_{12} + \hat{A}_{1i}^T E^T; \\ \bar{\Omega}_{26} &= \hat{A}_{1i}^T - V; \bar{\Omega}_{55} = W_{11} + W_{21} - sym(H_{11}); \bar{\Omega}_{56} = W_{12} + W_{22} - EV - H_{12}^T; \\ \bar{\Omega}_{66} &= W_{13} + W_{23} - sym(V); E = [I \quad 0]^T \end{aligned}$$

The following parameters as.

$$\hat{A}_{1i} = V^{-1}\check{A}_{1i}; \hat{A}_{2i} = V^{-1}\check{A}_{2i}; \hat{B}_{1i} = V^{-1}\check{B}_{1i}; \hat{B}_{2i} = V^{-1}\check{B}_{2i}; \hat{C}_i = \check{C}_i. \tag{26}$$

4.2. Proof 4.2

Parameterise slack matrices M_1, M_2, G_1, G_2, F_1 and H in Theorem 3.1 as.

$$M_1 = \begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & V \\ M_{12} & V \\ M_{13} & 0 \\ M_{14} & V \end{bmatrix}; G_2 = \begin{bmatrix} G_{21} & V \\ G_{22} & V \\ G_{23} & 0 \\ G_{24} & V \end{bmatrix}; M_2 = \begin{bmatrix} M_{21} & 0 \\ M_{22} & 0 \end{bmatrix}; G_1 = \begin{bmatrix} G_{11} & V \\ G_{12} & V \end{bmatrix};$$

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} F_{11} & V \\ F_{12} & V \end{bmatrix}, H = \begin{bmatrix} H_{11} & V \\ H_{12} & V \end{bmatrix} \quad (27)$$

4.3. Remark 4.3

If we take $Q_m = \text{diag}\{Q_{mh}, Q_{mv}\} = 0, m = 1, \dots, 3$, we can employ theorem 3 to settle the H_∞ filter for FMLSS nonlinear 2-D systems in EF range.

5. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

Consider a 2D discrete-time model, given by [19].

Rule 1: if $\zeta_1(s)$ is $\tilde{M}_1^1, \zeta_2(s)$ is $\tilde{M}_2^1$, then,

$$\begin{aligned} x_{n+1,k+1} &= A_{11}x_{n,k+1} + A_{21}x_{n+1,k} + B_{11}u_{n,k+1} + B_{21}u_{n+1,k} \\ y_{n,k} &= C_1x_{n,k} + D_1u_{n,k}; \\ z_{n,k} &= E_1x_{n,k} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Rule 2: if $\zeta_1(s)$ is $\tilde{M}_1^2, \zeta_2(s)$ is $\tilde{M}_2^2$, then,

$$\begin{aligned} x_{n+1,k+1} &= A_{12}x_{n,k+1} + A_{22}x_{n+1,k} + B_{12}u_{n,k+1} + B_{22}u_{n+1,k} \\ y_{n,k} &= C_2x_{n,k} + D_2u_{n,k}; \\ z_{n,k} &= E_1x_{n,k} \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} A_{11} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 & -0.2 \\ -0.2 & 0.1 \end{bmatrix}; A_{21} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.25 & 0.1 \\ -0.05 & 0.3 \end{bmatrix}; A_{12} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.3 & -0.2 \\ -0.2 & 0.3 \end{bmatrix}; A_{22} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.25 & 0.1 \\ -0.05 & 0.5 \end{bmatrix}; \\ B_{11} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 \\ 0.25 \end{bmatrix}; B_{12} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 \\ 0.4 \end{bmatrix}; D_1 = D_2 = 0.1; B_{21} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0.28 \end{bmatrix}; B_{22} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0.2 \end{bmatrix}; E_1 = E_2 = 0.1; \\ C_1 &= C_2 = [0 \quad 1] \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

The normalized membership function:

$$q_1(\zeta_{n,k}) = 1 - \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-2(\zeta_{n,k} - 3))}; q_2(\zeta_{n,k}) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-2(\zeta_{n,k} - 3))} \quad (31)$$

Suppose that the FF domain of disturbance input signal is $[\frac{\pi}{8}, \frac{\pi}{4}] \times [\frac{\pi}{8}, \frac{\pi}{4}]$. Via using Theorem 4, the obtained matrix parameters of FF H_∞ filter are the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{A}_{11} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.1454 & -0.1092 \\ 0.0638 & -0.2298 \end{bmatrix}; \check{B}_{11} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.3219 \\ 0.0002 \end{bmatrix}; \check{A}_{12} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.2454 & -0.0738 \\ 0.0010 & -0.0974 \end{bmatrix}; \check{B}_{21} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.0923 \\ -0.1105 \end{bmatrix}; \\ \check{A}_{21} &= \begin{bmatrix} -0.1527 & 0.7145 \\ 0.0305 & -0.2105 \end{bmatrix}; \check{B}_{12} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.1504 \\ 0.0204 \end{bmatrix}; \check{A}_{22} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.0101 & 0.8745 \\ 0.0174 & -0.0202 \end{bmatrix}; \check{B}_{22} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.0017 \\ 0.0201 \end{bmatrix}; \\ \check{C}_1 &= [-1.9560 \quad 0.4749]; \check{C}_2 = [-1.9560 \quad 0.4749]; \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

The comparison result with the technique proposed in Theorem 4.1 Illustrate in Table 1, that indicate the little conservation of the method suggest in the paper. Figures 1-3 indicate the path of states filters vectors $\hat{x}_1, \hat{x}_2$ and filtering error system of $e_{n,k}$, respectively. From Figures 1-3, also, we could notice whether the

error model is stable, knowing that the initial Condition are null, we can work out $\frac{\|e_{n,k}\|_2}{\|u_{n,k}\|_2} = 0.2205$. So, the condition (10) is fulfilled, that signify that the error system get a specific H_∞ index ($\gamma = 0.2357$).

Table 1. H_∞ performance apply from various approaches

Frequency domain	Methods	γ
$[0;\pi] \times [0;\pi]$	Theorem 6 in [26]	1.7302
$[0;\pi] \times [0;\pi]$	Theorem 3.4 (Q=0) in [19]	Inf
$[0;\pi] \times [0;\pi]$	Theorem 4.1 (Q=0)	0.6321
$[\frac{\pi}{8}; \frac{\pi}{4}] \times [\frac{\pi}{8}; \frac{\pi}{4}]$	Theorem 3.4 in [19]	0.6000
$[\frac{\pi}{8}; \frac{\pi}{4}] \times [\frac{\pi}{8}; \frac{\pi}{4}]$	Theorem 4.1	0.2357

Figure 1. Trajectory of state filter vectors $\hat{x}_1$

Figure 2. Trajectory of state filter vectors $\hat{x}_2$

Figure 3. Error $e_{n,k}$

6. CONCLUSION

This work, we dealt with problematic for the FF design of FMLSS nonlinear 2-D systems over FF ranges. We have suggested a filter process in order to minimize the conservatism design using the frequency information of the disturbances and we have assumed that the disturbances are known in a recognized FF domain. Also, systematic techniques have been suggested for the generation of a filtering which ensures asymptotic stability and FF H_∞ index, at the basis of a more general linearization procedure.

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